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THE ROLE OF IBRAHIM MOMINOV IN STUDYING THE PERSONALITY OF AMIR TEMUR

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ANNOTATION

The article discusses the services of academician Ibrahim Mominov in elucidating the personality of Amir Temur during the former Mustabid era. Academician Ibrahim Mominov was also classified as a person who cared for the fate of the nation and the people during the totalitarian regime. His concern about the possibility of awakening the nation through the spread of enlightenment and his tireless research were analyzed.

Key words: Amir Temur, academician, Ibrahim Mominov, period, ruler, system, enlightenment, people, nation, person, fate, science, country.

There are reasons why Amir Temur is immortal. First, as a skilled general, he united a disintegrating, fragmented state. He saved the country from the tyranny of the Mongols. Secondly, he patronized science, art, and culture, gathered talented people in various fields to Samarkand and created favorable conditions for their creativity. He rebuilt cities like Samarkand, Shahrisabz, Bukhara, Yassi. He repaired the cities of Baghdad and Darband, built waterways, fortifications, and cities in Iran, Azerbaijan,

and Afghanistan. This list can last long. He attached great importance to the development of science and culture with the help of thinkers who would lay the foundation stone for the future of the centralized state, not only to enrich the treasury. The development of religious and worldly sciences, folk art was able to rise to a new level.

Therefore, "Amir Temur has another great service to his country, people and history that cannot be stopped mentioning. Hazrat Sahibqiran raised and glorified the Motherland and its people in front of the whole world! Major countries such as Spain, Italy, England, France, and China recognized and recognized the land of Turkestan in the person of Amir Temur."¹

Any free creative thought, teaching contrary to the ideology of the Soviet Union was regarded as an enemy of the people, a nationalist, a traitor to the country. For this reason, the system of ideas promoted by the former union served not for the perfection of the individual, but on the contrary, to turn him into a zombies, deprived of free thinking, who only follows orders. This ideology, which is a counter weapon and a source of harmful worldview, has become an infamous past along with its time and system.

"Today, thanks to independence, an objective scientific approach to philosophy and the history of philosophical teachings has opened up. Knowing history, being able to draw correct and impartial conclusions from it is extremely important for the spiritual development of a person. After all, without knowing the past, it is impossible to correctly imagine the future."²

Indeed, as the First President of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, stated: "We must understand one thing well, having general and special knowledge, conscious, thinking free from various "isms", inheriting modern worldview, national and universal values. Only people are able to establish civil society and improve it further".³

¹ Ahmedov B. Remembering Amir Temur. T.: Uzbekistan, 1996, p. 132.

² Western philosophy. Compiler and editor-in-chief: Qiyamiddin Nazarov. - Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan, East, 2004. - p. 3.

³ Karimov I. We build our future with our own hands. T.: "Uzbekistan" 1999. p. 22.

"Universal human values are not by spreading the values of one nation to the whole world, but by comparing the values of all nations and peoples, respecting the values that the scale of history preserves, and realizing that national diversity in the world is inextricably linked with natural diversity." gets rich with li"¹

At the beginning of the 21st century, the process of globalization reached a new level thanks to information technologies, and the foreign influence on national values increased immeasurably. This influence, on the one hand, led to the enrichment of national cultures, reassessment and rise of values, and on the other hand, the introduction of customs and actions alien to the psyche and values of the nation.

Tolerance, mutual harmony, cultural-educational closeness are the national values characteristic of the multi-ethnic nation of Uzbekistan. It is known that moral qualities are formed as a factor of self-management of the people, ensuring the development of the society, bringing a mature person to adulthood and are passed from generation to generation.

On February 7, 2017, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's Decree "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was announced. This Decree of great historical and social importance noted and summarized the achievements in all fields during the years of independence. But from the point of view of today's globalization and worldly potential, which is characterized by high development, it becomes clear that there are still enough cases of poverty and poverty. As our head of state noted, at the same time, a deep analysis of the path of development of our country, today's world market conjuncture has changed dramatically, competition is intensifying in the conditions of globalization, a completely new approach and principles is developing for the development of our country at a more stable and rapid pace.²

¹ Shaikhova X, Nazarov K. Universal values and spiritual maturity. T.: Uzbekistan», 1992. p. 32

² People's word" February 8, 2017

I. Mominov was a scholar who worried about the fate of the nation and the people during the totalitarian regime, believing that it is possible to awaken the nation by spreading enlightenment, and was constantly sought after in this way.

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